

THE USAGE OF IRONY AND SARCASM IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LITERARY WORKS.

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the usage of irony and sarcasm in Uzbek and English literary works. Irony is a multifaceted and multifaceted phenomenon. It is the subject of study of philosophers, literary critics, linguists. There is even the term "ironology", as a field of science that studies irony. The stylistic device of irony aids in giving the artistic text meaning and adds fascination to the speech process. This study's focus is on the history of irony, the scientists who developed it, their theories, various kinds of irony, and its application in both spoken language and literal texts.

Key words: irony, literal text, sarcasm, cognitivism, cognitive linguistics, stylistic trop, linguistics.

INTRODUCTION

Irony is traditionally regarded as a category of the comic. Literary criticism has long dealt with the problem of the comic and its types. According to researchers, the underestimation of irony as an artistic form of critical assimilation of reality originates "in the indefinite status of irony, primarily in the system of the aesthetic category of the comic".¹ Humor, of which irony is a part, is reflected in the way of life of the people, their culture and language. Knowing and understanding the mechanisms of functioning of humor and irony is necessary to ensure effective intercultural communication.

¹ [Pokhodnya 1989:3-4].

Every writer's work possesses a trait that unites all of his works, which can be explained by the writer's outlook and the singularity of his perspectives on the world and man. In truth, the writer's works primarily express their attitude toward reality through lyricism and irony, or sarcasm.

In all spheres of conversation in the world's developed languages, including artistic discourse, the category of irony is used very frequently.

The creation of a very powerful and effective expression based on the comparison of a linguistic image of one real world with a fictional, false linguistic image of a particular speaker or writer is the primary characteristic of irony according to cognitive linguistics.

Main part

The term "irony" today denotes a variety of phenomena that are united by the idea of a discrepancy between the expected and real state of affairs. Researchers point to the discrepancy between the objective properties of an object and its norm that exists in our minds as the main premise of the comic.² Irony is also defined as the intentional transmission of insincerity towards an illocutionary act.

National humor, including irony, as well as other aspects of communication, have ethno-cultural specifics. It is associated with the national mentality, the vision of the world inherent in this people, and centuries-old traditions.

We consider the functions of irony and the language means of its expression, mainly in conflict-free interpersonal communication, the frequency of reference to irony by representatives of compared cultures, as well as the influence of irony on the formation of a national style of communication.

An important question in the study of irony is the following: does irony belong to language or is it an independent category? Some researchers resolve the issue of the complex relationship between irony and language in favor of excluding irony from the language system and giving it the status of a special channel for transmitting

² Dzemidok 1974, Propp 1997

information that needs specific conditions and uses the language code as one of the possibilities for meaning.³ This point of view is substantiated by the fact that irony functions in a specific situation based on the cognitive structures of the participants and, not being a unit of the language system, is implemented mainly using the language code. The signal of irony for the recipient is the contextual inappropriateness of what is reported. Such an approach does not seem to be entirely legitimate, since irony, in our opinion, should be perceived not as a fragment of the objective world in the form of an ironic situation, but as a linguistic phenomenon.

These two linguistic representations of the world—the main objective representation and the secondary subjective representation—show how flexible the world is and how language is an incredibly effective tool for perceiving reality. This is particularly clear in artistic discourse because neither its creator nor its consumer shares the same categories of thought, and neither does the world as it appears to each individual ever match the mental image that they have of it.

The scope of meaning of sarcasm is to some degree smaller than that of "irony". In this manner, when we come across meanings distinctive from "incongruity" communicated by the term "irony" within the considers of Western scientists, misunderstandings normally emerge. In modern Uzbek scholarly thinks about, the term "irony" is utilized as the Uzbek comparable of "irony". In spite of the fact that sarcasm is once in a while utilized as a metaphor, sarcasm as a stylistic tool is broadly utilized in discourse communication.

Sarcasm - bitter poison, ridicule, ridicule. Wry smiles and ridicule are the basis of sarcasm. A mode of expression widely used in lyrical, epic, and dramatic works, especially comedies. The irony comes from the portable his meaning that contradicts the original meaning of the word. In irony, intonation and the author's attitude to the subject play an important role. Sarcasm usually reveals the negative side of a person, thing, or event.

³ Varzonin 1994:11

Humor is one of the types of fiction; irony and sarcasm. Comic works are critical in spirit. In the past, Eastern peoples, including Uzbek literature, developed as an independent genre, mainly in poetry and folklore. They depict most of the bad aspects of society, as well as some groups or individuals. In irony or sarcasm, ironic mocking or exposing laughter directed at the criticized object determines the ideological content and artistic means of the work. Sarcasm can be written in different genres. For example, "Dead Souls" (N.V. Gogol) in the form of a comic novel, "Maysara's work" (Hamza), "Last Copies" (A. Qahhor) in the form of a comic play, "People with evil intentions" (A. Chekhov), "Udkhor's death" (S. Ayniy), "A sound from the grave" (A. Qahhor) in the form of a comic story, "Toyi Iqan bachcha" (Muqimi), "Hajvi yikchi eshan" (Zavqiy) in the form of a comic poem, "Our thoughts" (A. Qahhor) is written in the form of a sarcasm strip.⁴

Comic works are characterized by exaggeration of events, exaggeration and extensive use of fantasy. Irony and sarcasm serve to eliminate certain evils in the life of the society, to correct shortcomings, and to prevent them.

As a literary device, irony is often misunderstood. Although many of us learn about irony in our high school English classes through works of theater like Shakespeare's *Romeo and Juliet* or Sophocles' *Oedipus Rex*, many people feel unsure of what irony means—or how to use it correctly. For example, the difference between what something appears to mean versus its literal meaning. Irony, in its broadest sense, is a rhetorical device, literary technique, or event characterized by an incongruity, or contrast, between reality (what is) and appearance (what seems to be). The ironic form of simile, used in sarcasm, and some forms of litotes can emphasize one's meaning by the deliberate use of language which states the opposite of the truth, denies the contrary of the truth, or drastically and obviously understates a factual connection.

With irony, unlike most literary tropes, readers are let in on the joke. They see and know things of which the characters themselves are not aware. Thus, it gives them

⁴ file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/1234-Article%20Text-2368-1-10-20220410%20(1).pdf
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a sense of distance from the story. This allows them to parse the ideas and themes that are being expressed in ways that are not always readily available in stories that do not employ the use of irony. Irony also allows readers to understand characters in ways that the characters don't know of themselves. For example, the irony in Shakespeare's *King Lear* allows audiences to understand the kind of hubris that *King Lear* represents and also allows them to understand how this hubris leads to his downfall.

In sarcasm, intonation and the author's attitude to the object of the image play an important role. Usually, sarcasm reveals the negative aspects of a person, thing, or event. The so-called types of sarcasm (bitter sneering, sarcastic mocking, hinting) and irony (mockery, denial of this or that positive trait through laughter) vary from one another.

The writings of Abdullah Qahhor, a master of words and a revered author of our people, contain sporadic instances of sarcasm. He used different types of irony to create distinctive images in his humorous tales and feuilletons, such as "Mayiz yemagan khotin" (The Woman Who Didn't Eat Raisins), "Adabiyot muallimi" (The Teacher of Literature), and "Nutq" (Speech). For example, the image of Mulla Norkuzi, depicted in ironic colors in the author's story "Mayiz yemagan khotin", is one of such characters:

1. When the war broke out she took down the signed photograph of the Kaiser and, with some solemnity, hung it in the men-servants' lavatory; it was her one combative action. (E. W.)

2. "I had a plot, a scheme, a little quiet piece of enjoyment afoot, of which the very cream and essence was that this old man and grandchild should be as poor as frozen rats," and Mr. Brass revealed the whole story, making himself out to be rather a saint like holy character. (D.)

3. "She's a charming middle-aged lady with a face like a bucket of mud and if she has washed her hair since Coolidge's second term, I'll eat my spare tire, rim and all." (R. Ch.)⁵

Conclusion.

Examples in Uzbek and English are provided in the text as evidence of our claims. It is clear from the article that a work produced without stylistic devices and means of expression will stay a straightforward text. But even if the stylistic devices and means of expression are not used correctly, the literary work loses its significance. Of course, the writer's writing manner and proficiency with stylistic colors play a significant part in this.

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